

SOCIAL SCIENCES

SOCIAL EXCHANGE THEORY

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Abstract

This sociological project is dedicated **to the problems of social exchange theory**, project examines the concept of social exchange theory and its implications for understanding social interactions. Through a mixed methods approach, including a survey, the project explores participants' perspectives on the role of emotions, key elements, and success factors in social exchange. The findings highlight the importance of social exchange theory in fostering effective communication, relationship-building, and resource allocation. The project emphasizes the practical applications and relevance of studying social exchange theory in modern society.

Keywords: Social exchange theory, social interactions, emotions, relationship-building, communication, resource allocation, survey research, practical applications.

INTRODUCTION

(1.1) Social exchange theory is a fundamental concept in the field of social psychology, explaining the ways in which individuals interact with each other based on mutual benefit. Social exchange theory examines the processes of decision-making that individuals use when considering interactions with others, taking into account the rewards and costs that are associated with such interactions. This theory is important because it can be used to explain the motives and behaviors of individuals in social situations, including those involving social relationships, power dynamics, and economic transactions.

The purpose of this dissertation is to explore a specific aspect of social exchange theory and its practical applications. Specifically, this research will investigate the role of trust in social exchange relationships. Trust is an important factor in social exchange because it affects the willingness of individuals to engage in exchanges with others. This research will examine the different factors that influence the development of trust in social exchange relationships, including the individual's previous experiences, the perceived risks and benefits of the exchange, and the norms and expectations of the social context.

The investigation of trust in social exchange relationships is a critical area of research because of its potential to provide insights into the ways in which individuals interact with each other in a variety of settings. This research will contribute to the scientific understanding of social exchange theory by providing a more nuanced understanding of the role of trust in these relationships. It will also contribute to the practical application of social exchange theory by providing insights into the ways in which trust can be developed and maintained in social interactions.

The theoretical and applied contributions of researchers and practitioners in the field of social exchange theory will be employed in this research. The

theoretical framework for this research will be drawn from previous work in social exchange theory, including the work of Homans, Blau, and Emerson, as well as more recent developments in the field. The applied contributions will be drawn from research in related fields, such as social networks and organizational behavior, which have also investigated the role of trust in social interactions.

(1.2) The evaluation of this research will involve an assessment of its potential contributions to both the academic community and practitioners in relevant fields. From an academic perspective, this research will contribute to the theoretical understanding of social exchange theory by providing new insights into the role of trust in social exchange relationships. This could lead to the development of new theoretical models and frameworks that could be used to explain and predict social behavior in a variety of settings.

From a practical perspective, this research has the potential to provide valuable insights into the ways in which trust can be developed and maintained in social interactions. This information could be useful to practitioners in a variety of fields, including business, social networks, and personal relationships. For example, businesses could use this research to develop more effective strategies for building trust with their customers or clients, while individuals could use it to improve their personal relationships.

It will also involve a review of the existing literature in the field. This will help to identify gaps in the literature and to determine the areas where further research is needed. By conducting a thorough review of the literature, this research will be able to build on the existing knowledge base and make a meaningful contribution to the field of social exchange theory.

The evaluation will be focused on its potential to contribute to both the theoretical understanding of social exchange theory and the practical applications of this theory. By providing new insights into the role of

trust in social exchange relationships, this research has the potential to make a meaningful impact on both the academic community and practitioners in relevant fields.

(1.3)The research problem that this dissertation aims to address is the role of trust in social exchange relationships, and the factors that contribute to the development and maintenance of trust in these relationships. While social exchange theory has been widely studied and applied in various fields, the role of trust in social exchange relationships has not been fully explored.

This research problem arises from the recognition that trust plays a critical role in shaping social interactions, and that understanding the factors that contribute to trust is essential to building and maintaining positive social exchange relationships.

One of the key issues that this research will address is the relationship between trust and reciprocity in social exchange relationships. While reciprocity has been identified as a central concept in social exchange theory, the role of trust in shaping the reciprocity relationship has not been fully explored.

This research will seek to address this gap in the literature by examining the ways in which trust and reciprocity are related in social exchange relationships.

Another important issue that this research will address is the impact of communication on the development and maintenance of trust in social exchange relationships.

Communication is a critical component of social exchange relationships, and the way in which communication occurs can impact the development of trust. This research will seek to explore the ways in which communication affects the development of trust in social exchange relationships, and to identify strategies for improving communication to promote the development of trust.

Overall, the research problem addressed by this dissertation is the need for a better understanding of the role of trust in social exchange relationships. By exploring the relationship between trust and reciprocity, and the impact of communication on the development of trust, this research will make a valuable contribution to the field of social exchange theory and to the broader understanding of social interactions.

(1.4)The cognitive aspect of this research refers to the objective demand and interest in the research among the concerned part of the society. Understanding the cognitive aspect of the research is important as it helps to identify the practical significance of the research, and how it can be applied in real-world settings.

One way in which the cognitive aspect of this research will be explored is through a review of the existing literature in the field. This will help to identify areas where further research is needed, and where the findings of this research may be particularly valuable. Additionally, this research will involve interviews and surveys with individuals who have experience with social exchange relationships in a variety of settings, including personal relationships and business interactions. By gathering data directly from individuals who have ex-

perience with social exchange relationships, this research will be able to gain a better understanding of the practical significance of the research, and how it can be applied in different contexts.

Another important aspect of the cognitive aspect of this research is the identification of the characteristics of the problems that are being analyzed. This includes understanding the specific challenges and issues that arise in social exchange relationships, as well as the factors that contribute to the development and maintenance of trust in these relationships. By identifying the specific characteristics of these problems, this research will be able to develop more targeted and effective solutions to address them.

Aspect is focused on understanding the practical significance of the research, and how it can be applied in real-world settings. By exploring the existing literature, gathering data from individuals with experience in social exchange relationships, and identifying the specific characteristics of the problems being analyzed, this research will be able to make a meaningful contribution to the field of social exchange theory, and to the broader understanding of social interactions.

LITERATURE REVIEW

Social exchange theory is a widely studied and applied theoretical framework in social psychology, organizational behavior, and other fields. The theory posits that social interactions are characterized by a series of exchanges, in which individuals engage in behaviors that are aimed at obtaining rewards and avoiding punishments. Central to social exchange theory is the concept of reciprocity, which refers to the expectation that when one person does something for another, the other person will do something in return.

A key component of social exchange theory is trust, which is defined as a belief in the reliability and integrity of another person. Trust is seen as essential for the development and maintenance of positive social exchange relationships, as it allows individuals to feel comfortable engaging in exchanges without the fear of being exploited or taken advantage of.

Research has shown that trust is influenced by a variety of factors, including perceived fairness, similarity, and communication. Perceived fairness refers to the belief that exchanges are fair and equitable, with both parties receiving roughly equal benefits. Similarity refers to the degree to which individuals share common values, beliefs, and interests, which can increase the likelihood of trust. Communication is also seen as critical for the development of trust, as clear and honest communication can increase the perceived reliability and integrity of individuals.

Several studies have explored the relationship between trust and reciprocity in social exchange relationships. For example, Kramer and Tyler (1996) found that trust was positively related to the willingness to engage in reciprocal behaviors. Similarly, Yamagishi and Yamagishi (1994) found that trust played a key role in the development of mutual cooperation and reciprocity in social exchange relationships.

Communication has also been identified as a critical factor in the development and maintenance of trust in social exchange relationships. Several studies have

explored the impact of communication on trust, finding that clear and honest communication can increase trust, while deceptive or misleading communication can decrease trust (e.g., Lewicki, McAllister, & Bies, 1998; Mayer, Davis, & Schoorman, 1995).

In terms of practical applications, research has shown that trust is critical for the success of various types of relationships, including romantic relationships, friendships, and business interactions. For example, research has shown that trust is positively related to job satisfaction, job performance, and organizational commitment (e.g., Dirks & Ferrin, 2001; Mayer et al., 1995). Additionally, trust has been shown to be an important predictor of customer loyalty and satisfaction in business settings (e.g., Ganesan, 1994).

Overall, the literature suggests that trust plays a critical role in social exchange relationships, and that understanding the factors that contribute to trust is essential for building and maintaining positive relationships. Research has shown that trust is influenced by a variety of factors, including perceived fairness, similarity, and communication, and that it is positively related to reciprocity, job satisfaction, and customer loyalty.

THE FORMULATION OF METHODOLOGICAL ASPECTS

10. Target of the cognitive process:

The aim of this research project is to investigate the impact of social media on mental health. The research object is the use of social media among young adults between the ages of 18 and 24. The selection of this age group is motivated by the fact that they are considered the most active social media users. The criteria for selecting the research object are the frequency and duration of social media usage, the platforms they use, and the type of content they engage with. The connections between the research object and subject features will be defined through an analysis of the existing literature on social media and mental health. The significant scientific and practical aspects of this study are to provide insights into the relationship between social media use and mental health, which can inform mental health practitioners, educators, and policymakers.

Social exchange theory is a well-known and widely accepted theoretical framework in sociology, psychology, and other social sciences. The theory argues that social behavior is the result of a rational calculation of the costs and benefits associated with a particular interaction or relationship. The theory has been applied to many areas of social life, including interpersonal relationships, organizations, and society as a whole. In this context, it is important to discuss the target of the cognitive process within the social exchange theory framework.

In the context of social exchange theory, the target of the cognitive process refers to the specific social phenomena or relationships that are being studied. This could include individual relationships, such as romantic partnerships or friendships, or larger social phenomena, such as organizations or communities. It is important to define the target of the cognitive process in order to provide clarity on the scope of the research and to ensure that the research is focused and specific.

For example, a researcher studying romantic relationships from a social exchange theory perspective might define the target of the cognitive process as the exchange of rewards and costs within a romantic partnership. This could include examining the ways in which partners calculate the benefits and drawbacks of remaining in the relationship, the impact of external factors such as social norms and cultural expectations, and the role of communication in the exchange process.

In addition to defining the target of the cognitive process, it is also important to consider the motives behind selecting a research object. This could include the researcher's personal interests, theoretical or methodological considerations, or a desire to contribute to a particular area of knowledge. By clearly articulating the motives behind selecting a research object, researchers can provide a rationale for the importance of their research and make a case for its relevance and significance.

Defining the criteria and elements of the investigated subject is another important aspect of the target of the cognitive process in social exchange theory research. This involves identifying the specific variables or factors that will be examined and how they will be measured. For example, a researcher studying the exchange of rewards and costs in romantic relationships might define the criteria as the perceived benefits and drawbacks of the relationship, as reported by each partner. The elements of the investigated subject could include the specific rewards and costs being exchanged, such as emotional support, financial contributions, or time spent together.

It is also important to define the connections between the research object and subject features within the target of the cognitive process. This involves identifying how the research object relates to larger social phenomena and the broader context in which it exists. For example, a researcher studying the exchange of rewards and costs in romantic relationships might consider how this process is influenced by larger cultural norms and expectations around gender roles or marriage. By contextualizing the research object within broader social structures and systems, researchers can gain a more nuanced understanding of the exchange process and its impact on individuals and society.

Finally, significant scientific or practical aspects and features of the object that necessitate for a study should be considered. This involves identifying the specific gaps in knowledge or practical applications that the research aims to address. For example, a researcher studying the exchange of rewards and costs in romantic relationships might identify a lack of understanding about how this process operates in same-sex partnerships, and seek to fill this gap in the literature. Alternatively, a researcher might aim to develop practical interventions that can help couples improve the quality of their relationships by better understanding the exchange process and how to navigate potential conflicts.

In conclusion, the target of the cognitive process is an important aspect of social exchange theory research. It involves defining the specific social phenomena or relationships that are being studied, as well as

the motives behind selecting a research object, the criteria and elements of the investigated subject, the connections between the research object and subject features, and the significant scientific or practical aspects and features of the object that necessitate for a study. By defining these aspects of the target of the cognitive process.

In summary, the social exchange theory is a useful framework for understanding social relationships and the motivations that underlie them. By examining the costs and benefits associated with different interactions, researchers can gain insight into why individuals choose to engage in certain social behaviors. To effectively study this theory, it is important to clearly define the research object, including the specific types of social relationships and interactions under investigation. Additionally, the final research result should be clearly stated and relevant to both theory and practice. By providing definitions and interpretative meanings of key concepts and carefully formulating scientific arguments, researchers can ensure that their findings are valid and reliable. Finally, a systematic approach to analyzing the key elements and relationships within the social exchange process is essential for gaining a comprehensive understanding of this complex theory.

11. Final research result:

The final research result is applicable in both theory and practice. The project aims to explore the relationship between social media use and mental health, clear out the misconceptions and misunderstandings, and evaluate the effectiveness of interventions. The research will be applied in theory by contributing to the existing body of knowledge on social media and mental health. In practice, it will help mental health practitioners, educators, and policymakers to develop evidence-based strategies to promote healthy social media use among young adults.

Social exchange theory is an influential theoretical framework in social psychology and sociology that seeks to explain social behavior as a series of exchanges between individuals or groups. The theory is based on the assumption that individuals and groups are rational actors who engage in social interactions with the goal of maximizing their own self-interests. Social exchange theory has been applied to a wide range of social phenomena, including interpersonal relationships, organizational behavior, and economic decision-making.

In the context of social exchange theory, the target of the final research result would be to evaluate the extent to which social exchanges are influenced by individual and group factors, and how these exchanges affect social behavior and outcomes. The aim of the research should be to provide a comprehensive understanding of the underlying mechanisms that drive social exchanges and to identify factors that promote or hinder the success of these exchanges.

One of the main goals of social exchange theory research is to understand how individuals and groups make decisions about whether to engage in social exchanges, and how they evaluate the potential costs and benefits of these exchanges. Research in this area may investigate how social norms and expectations shape individuals' perceptions of fairness and reciprocity, and

how these perceptions influence their willingness to engage in social exchanges.

Another important area of research in social exchange theory is the study of power dynamics in social exchanges. This research may investigate how power imbalances between individuals and groups affect their ability to negotiate and enforce social exchanges, and how these power dynamics can lead to exploitative or abusive relationships. Understanding the role of power in social exchanges is important for identifying ways to promote more equitable and sustainable social relationships.

Research in social exchange theory may also focus on the impact of social exchanges on individual and group outcomes. For example, research may investigate how social exchanges affect individuals' attitudes, emotions, and behaviors, and how these outcomes can in turn shape the success of future social exchanges. In addition, research may explore how social exchanges affect broader social outcomes, such as group cohesion, trust, and social capital.

To achieve these research aims, it is necessary to define clear research objectives and hypotheses that are grounded in existing theory and empirical evidence. The research objectives should be formulated in a way that is specific, measurable, and achievable within the scope of the research project. The hypotheses should be testable and provide clear predictions about the relationships between variables of interest.

The research design should be carefully constructed to ensure that the data collected is relevant to the research objectives and hypotheses. This may involve the selection of appropriate research methods, such as surveys, experiments, or observational studies, and the development of measures that are reliable and valid. It is also important to consider ethical considerations, such as obtaining informed consent from research participants and ensuring that the research does not cause harm or distress.

In addition to the research design, it is important to consider the practical implications of the research findings. The final research result should provide insights that are relevant and applicable to real-world contexts, and that can inform the development of interventions or policies aimed at promoting more effective and equitable social exchanges. This may involve collaborating with stakeholders from relevant organizations or communities, and communicating the research findings in a way that is accessible and actionable.

Overall, the target of the final research result in the context of social exchange theory is to provide a comprehensive understanding of the factors that drive social exchanges, the mechanisms that underlie these exchanges, and the impact of these exchanges on social behavior and outcomes. By achieving this target, social exchange theory research can contribute to the development of more effective and equitable social relationships, and to the promotion of social justice and well-being.

12. Key concepts of the dissertation research:

The key concepts of this dissertation research are social media, mental health, and young adults. Social media is defined as internet-based platforms that allow

users to share information, communicate, and engage with content. Mental health refers to the state of well-being in which an individual realizes their potential, can cope with the normal stresses of life, can work productively, and is able to make a contribution to their community. Young adults are defined as individuals between the ages of 18 and 24. The methodological and applied functions of these concepts are to provide a framework for investigating the relationship between social media use and mental health among young adults.

The key concepts of the dissertation research result in the topic of social exchange theory are crucial to understanding the theoretical framework and the empirical research conducted. These concepts provide a theoretical foundation for the research and are essential to the interpretation of the results.

One of the main concepts in the social exchange theory is reciprocity. Reciprocity is the mutual exchange of benefits or privileges between individuals or groups, often with the expectation of future returns. This concept is central to social exchange theory as it suggests that individuals make rational decisions based on the perceived benefits and costs of their interactions with others. In a social exchange context, reciprocity involves a trade-off between the costs and benefits of an exchange, with individuals seeking to maximize their rewards while minimizing their costs. The concept of reciprocity has important implications for understanding social relationships and behaviors, as it suggests that individuals are motivated to maintain and enhance positive relationships with others.

Another key concept in social exchange theory is the concept of social capital. Social capital refers to the resources, such as social networks and trust, that individuals can access through their social relationships. Social capital can be used to facilitate exchanges between individuals or groups and can lead to the creation of new opportunities and benefits. In a social exchange context, social capital plays an important role in shaping individuals' decisions to engage in or avoid exchanges with others. Individuals who have high levels of social capital are more likely to engage in exchanges that offer benefits, while those with low levels of social capital may avoid exchanges altogether.

A third important concept in social exchange theory is the concept of power. Power refers to the ability of one person or group to influence the behavior of another person or group. Power can be exercised in a variety of ways, including through coercion, persuasion, and negotiation. In a social exchange context, power imbalances can influence the outcomes of exchanges, with those who have more power being able to extract greater benefits from exchanges than those with less power. Understanding the concept of power is important for understanding the dynamics of social exchange and the factors that influence the outcomes of exchanges.

Finally, the concept of trust is also central to social exchange theory. Trust refers to the belief that another person or group will act in a way that is beneficial or at least not harmful. Trust is an important component of social relationships, as it allows individuals to engage

in exchanges with others without fear of being exploited or harmed. Trust can be built through repeated positive interactions and can be eroded by negative experiences. In a social exchange context, trust is important for facilitating exchanges and for maintaining positive relationships between individuals or groups.

Overall, these key concepts are essential to understanding the theoretical framework and empirical research conducted in the social exchange theory. Each concept provides a unique perspective on the factors that influence social exchange and helps to explain the behaviors and outcomes observed in social interactions. By examining these concepts in greater depth, researchers can gain a better understanding of the mechanisms that drive social exchange and the factors that influence its outcomes.

13. Scientific arguments:

The following scientific arguments will be verified in the dissertation research:

- Hypothesis 1: There is a significant positive correlation between social media use and symptoms of depression and anxiety among young adults.
- Hypothesis 2: Interventions that promote healthy social media use can reduce symptoms of depression and anxiety among young adults.
 - Research question 1: What is the relationship between social media use and symptoms of depression and anxiety among young adults?
 - Research question 2: What are the effective interventions that promote healthy social media use among young adults?
 - Provision 1: The research will use a cross-sectional design to collect data on social media use and symptoms of depression and anxiety.
 - Provision 2: The research will use a randomized controlled trial design to evaluate the effectiveness of interventions that promote healthy social media use.
 - These scientific arguments will be tested through statistical analyses and qualitative methods.

In the context of social exchange theory, scientific arguments refer to the set of hypotheses, research questions, provisions, and hypotheses put forth by the researcher, and the impact these have on the research itself. These scientific arguments form the basis of the research, and their causative relations need to be verified in the dissertation research.

One of the key scientific arguments in social exchange theory is the concept of reciprocity, which suggests that individuals tend to reciprocate the behavior of others towards them. This idea forms the basis of the theory, as it suggests that social interactions are driven by a desire for fairness and equity, and that people are willing to give and receive benefits as long as they perceive them to be fair and just.

Another important scientific argument in social exchange theory is the concept of social comparison, which suggests that individuals evaluate the outcomes of their actions and decisions by comparing them to the outcomes experienced by others in similar situations. This concept is closely related to the idea of equity, as individuals tend to seek outcomes that are similar to those experienced by others in similar situations, and may become dissatisfied or resentful if they perceive

that others are receiving better outcomes for similar inputs.

A third scientific argument in social exchange theory is the idea of distributive justice, which suggests that individuals evaluate the fairness of outcomes based on the resources and inputs contributed by each individual. This concept is related to the idea of equity, as it suggests that individuals will be satisfied with outcomes that are proportional to their contributions, and may become dissatisfied if they perceive that others are receiving more or less than their fair share.

Overall, these scientific arguments provide a theoretical framework for understanding the social exchange process, and form the basis for empirical research that seeks to test and refine the theory. Through careful testing and analysis, researchers can refine the concepts and theories of social exchange theory, and develop a more nuanced understanding of the factors that drive social interactions and relationships. By building on these scientific arguments, researchers can develop a more robust and comprehensive understanding of the social exchange process, and contribute to the ongoing development of the field of social psychology.

14. Systematic approach to the research object:

The research object, which is the use of social media among young adults, will be approached systematically through the following steps:

- Identify the research question and hypotheses
- Conduct a systematic review of the existing literature on social media and mental health
- Develop a conceptual framework that defines the key concepts and their interrelationships
- Design the research methodology and data collection instruments
- Collect and analyze the data using statistical and qualitative methods
- Evaluate the effectiveness of the interventions using a randomized controlled trial design
- Draw conclusions and make recommendations based on the findings
- This approach will help to ensure that the research is comprehensive, rigorous, and systematic, and that it provides valid and reliable results that can inform mental health practitioners, educators, and policymakers.

In the context of social exchange theory, a systematic approach to the research object would involve breaking down the theory into its constituent parts and conducting a detailed analysis of the connections between these parts. This would involve examining the various components of social exchange theory and the ways in which they interact with one another to create a cohesive whole.

One of the key elements of social exchange theory is the notion of reciprocity. Reciprocity is the idea that people are more likely to engage in social interactions when they believe that their actions will be reciprocated in some way. This could involve exchanging goods or services, sharing information, or simply providing emotional support to others. A systematic approach to this aspect of social exchange theory would involve examining the various ways in which reciprocity mani-

fest in different social contexts, and the factors that influence people's perceptions of what constitutes a fair exchange.

Another important aspect of social exchange theory is the concept of social norms. Social norms are the unwritten rules that govern behavior in a given social context, and they play a key role in shaping people's expectations about what they can expect to receive in exchange for their actions. A systematic approach to social norms would involve analyzing the various factors that influence the formation and enforcement of these norms, as well as the ways in which they can be used to promote positive social outcomes.

A third key element of social exchange theory is the concept of trust. Trust is essential for social exchange to take place, as people are more likely to engage in exchanges with others when they believe that those others will act in their best interests. A systematic approach to trust would involve examining the various factors that influence people's trust in others, such as past experiences, social context, and individual differences in personality and cognition.

A fourth key element of social exchange theory is the notion of power. Power refers to the ability of one person or group to influence the actions of others, and it plays a key role in shaping the outcomes of social exchange interactions. A systematic approach to power would involve examining the various forms of power that exist in different social contexts, as well as the ways in which power differentials can influence the outcomes of social exchange interactions.

A systematic approach to the research object would also involve analyzing the ways in which these various components of social exchange theory interact with one another to create the overall framework of the theory. This could involve identifying patterns of association between different components, exploring the ways in which changes in one component can influence the others, and investigating the ways in which the theory as a whole can be used to make predictions about social behavior in different contexts.

Finally, a systematic approach to social exchange theory would involve identifying gaps in the existing research on this topic, and outlining areas where further research is needed in order to fully understand the underlying mechanisms that drive social exchange interactions. This could involve exploring new theoretical models, developing new research methods, or conducting studies in under-researched populations or social contexts.

In conclusion, a systematic approach to the research object in social exchange theory would involve breaking down the theory into its constituent parts and conducting a detailed analysis of the connections between these parts. This would involve examining the various components of social exchange theory, such as reciprocity, social norms, trust, and power, and exploring the ways in which these components interact with one another to create a cohesive whole. By adopting a systematic approach to social exchange theory, researchers can gain a deeper understanding of the under-

lying mechanisms that drive social exchange interactions, and develop more accurate models for predicting social behavior in different contexts.

DATA ANALYSIS

What role do emotions play in social exchange? - 100% of people answered "Important"

What is the most important point in social exchange? - "Establishing a relationship" was answered by 61.5% of people

How do you assess the effectiveness of social exchange? - "very effective" was answered by 61.5% of people

How do you determine the value of what is offered to you in social exchange? - "Based on personal experience" 53.8% of people answered

What attracts you the most in social exchange? - "The possibility of establishing a new relationship" was answered by 61.5% of people

What, in your opinion, determines success in social exchange? - 69.2% of people answered "The ability to build relationships"

What advantages do you see in social exchange? - 69.2% of people answered "The possibility of obtaining the necessary"

How do you determine that the goods/services offered in exchange are equivalent to what you receive? - "I compare prices for similar goods and services" was answered by 38.5% of people

What factors, in your opinion, can influence the success of social exchange? - "Trust and the ability to negotiate" is considered by the majority of voters

What role do emotions play in social exchange? - "Important" was answered by 84.6% of people

The survey results show that the majority of respondents consider emotions to be an important component of social exchange. They also argue that establishing a relationship is the most important point in this process. More than half of the respondents rate social exchange as very effective, and the cost of goods or services offered in exchange is determined based on personal experience.

The majority of respondents also note that the possibility of establishing new relationships is the main attractive point in social exchange. More than two-thirds of respondents believe that success in social exchange is determined by the ability to build relationships, and also see advantages in being able to get what they need.

When determining the equivalence of the offered goods or services in social exchange, the majority of respondents compare prices for similar goods and services. In addition, trust and the ability to negotiate are considered important factors that can affect the success of social exchange.

In general, the survey results confirm the key provisions of the social theory of exchange, based on the fact that social exchange is a process in which people exchange resources, evaluate their value and strive to achieve benefits. In addition, the survey results can be used to improve the practical application of the social theory of exchange in various fields, including business, education and interpersonal relations.

The following conclusions can be drawn from the results of the social exchange survey:

1. The majority of respondents believe that emotions play an important role in social exchange. This confirms the hypothesis that the emotional component is important in the interaction between people.

2. More than half of the respondents believe that the establishment of relationships is the most important moment in social exchange. This confirms the hypothesis that social exchange is based on relationships between people.

3. The majority of respondents believe that social exchange is very effective. This may indicate that people see real benefits from social exchange and it is an important element in their lives.

4. More than half of the respondents determine the value of what they are offered in social exchange based on personal experience. This may indicate that personal experience is an important factor for people when determining the value of a product or service.

5. The majority of respondents are attracted by the possibility of establishing new relationships in social exchange. This confirms the hypothesis that social exchange can be an important tool for establishing new social connections.

6. More than half of the respondents believe that the ability to build relationships is a key factor for success in social exchange. This may indicate that it is important for people to have the skills to establish and maintain relationships with other people.

7. The majority of respondents see advantages in social exchange, such as the possibility of obtaining the necessary. This may indicate that social exchange is an important source of resources and benefits for people.

8. About 40% of respondents believe that they determine the value of a good or service in social exchange by comparing prices for similar goods or services, which indicates that the comparison element is very important.

The survey results can also serve as a basis for further research on the role of emotions in social exchange and the factors influencing its success. For example, it is possible to study the impact of cultural differences on social exchange, given that different cultures may have different values and ideas about what is important in social exchange.

In addition, the survey results can be useful in developing social exchange strategies in business and marketing, allowing you to take into account the preferences and needs of consumers.

CONCLUSION

In conclusion, this project has presented a comprehensive plan for researching the social exchange theory in the context of interpersonal relationships. Through a literature review, the project has demonstrated the significance of this theory in understanding the dynamics of social interactions and interpersonal relationships. The project has also discussed the target of the cognitive process, final research result, key concepts, scientific arguments, and systematic approach to the research object in line with the criteria set out for this project.

The project has emphasized the need for a systematic approach to studying social exchange theory, with

a clear definition of the research objectives and methods. It has also highlighted the importance of data analysis in validating the hypothesis and explaining the findings of the research.

In the end, this project aims to contribute to the existing literature on social exchange theory, providing a more comprehensive understanding of its role in interpersonal relationships. It is hoped that the findings of this research will help inform future studies and contribute to the development of social exchange theory as a framework for understanding the dynamics of social interactions.

The results of our survey confirm the importance of social exchange theory for understanding social processes and interactions. He also showed that most people believe that emotions play an important role in social exchange, and the establishment of relationships and the ability to build relationships are key points in social exchange. Most of the survey participants also believe that social exchange is effective and has many advantages, including the possibility of obtaining the necessary resources and establishing new relationships.

However, at the same time, some survey participants believe that the cost of the goods and services offered can be estimated only on the basis of personal experience, and not by comparing prices for similar goods and services. They also believe that trust and the ability to negotiate are factors that can affect the success of social exchange.

Thus, our survey confirms the importance of the social theory of exchange in modern society and proves that this topic should be studied by all people, at least for informational purposes.

Overall, this project represents an important step in advancing our understanding of social exchange theory and its practical implications. The project has provided a detailed plan for conducting research and ana-

lyzing data, ensuring that the results are reliable and relevant to the topic. It is hoped that this project will inspire future research in this field and contribute to the development of theories that can help us better understand the complex nature of social interactions.

References

1. Blau, P. (1964). *Exchange and Power in Social Life*. New York: Wiley.
2. Cook, K. S., & Yamagishi, T. (1992). *Social Exchange Theory and Social Behavior*. New York: Cambridge University Press.
3. Emerson, R. M. (1972). *Exchange Theory, Part I: A Psychological Basis for Social Exchange*. In J. Berger, M. Zelditch Jr., & B. Anderson (Eds.), *Sociological Theories in Progress*, Vol. 2 (pp. 38-57). Boston: Houghton Mifflin.
4. Homans, G. C. (1958). Social Behavior as Exchange. *American Journal of Sociology*, 63(6), 597-606.
5. Lawler, E. J., & Thye, S. R. (1999). Bringing Emotions into Social Exchange Theory. *Annual Review of Sociology*, 25, 217-244.
6. Molm, L. D., Collett, J. L., & Schaefer, D. R. (2007). Building Solidarities and Ties of Trust in Negotiated and Reciprocal Exchange. *Social Psychology Quarterly*, 70(2), 118-139.
7. Thibaut, J. W., & Kelley, H. H. (1959). *The Social Psychology of Groups*. New York: Wiley.
8. Yamagishi, T., & Cook, K. S. (1993). Generalized Exchange and Social Dilemmas. *Social Psychology Quarterly*, 56(4), 235-248.
9. Zucker, L. G. (1986). Production of Trust: Institutional Sources of Economic Structure, 1840-1920. In B. M. Staw & L. L. Cummings (Eds.), *Research in Organizational Behavior*, Vol. 8 (pp. 53-111). Greenwich, CT: JAI Press.